

Polarographic behaviour of Mo(VI) at dropping Mercury Electrode in Aqueous H₂SO₄ and Polarographic Determination of Molybdenum in presence of Vanadium

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Polarographic behaviour of molybdenum shows that three waves are obtained for the reduction of Mo(VI) to Mo(III) in aqueous H₂SO₄ using sodium sulphate as supporting electrolyte. The half wave potentials of the waves obtained are +0.06, -0.29 and -0.60 volts. The effects of change of mercury pressure, temperature and concentration have been studied and the results reveal that the waves are diffusion controlled but irreversible. A method has also been developed for the determination of molybdenum in presence of vanadium.

It is well known that the polarography of molybdenum is complex. The origin of this complexity may be traced to several such causes as the different oxidation states, the dissimilar reduction characteristic in different mineral acids and the catalytic nature of the waves from the solutions containing oxidizing agents. Polarographic studies of Mo(VI) in concentrated sulphuric acid have been done by Kolthoff and Hodara¹. Viecek² has reported two waves in concentrated sulphuric acid at potentials +0.19 volts and -0.05 volts vs. NCE. Hokhshtein³ and Holtje and Geyer⁴ have investigated the polarographic behaviour of Mo(VI) in weakly acidic solutions. Marvin *et al*⁵ have studied the polarographic reduction of Mo(VI) in aqueous sulphuric acid and sodium sulphate as base electrolyte. The purpose of the present investigation is to study the reduction wave of Mo(VI) in aqueous sulphuric acid in details and to develop a precise and rapid method for the determination of Mo(VI) in presence of vanadium(V), as such studies are not encountered within literature.

Apparatus: The polarographic data were obtained with a manual polarograph solamp galvanometer as current recorder in all these determinations. An H-type cell fitted with a saturated calomel reference electrode and an agar saturated potassium chloride salt bridge were used.

Purified hydrogen was passed through the experimental solutions to remove dissolved oxygen.

The capillary having the characteristics $m=0.3$ mg/sec, $t=3.24$ sec and $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 4.418$ mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/6} was used in all these determinations.

All the reagents used were of reagent grade and solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

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The cell was kept in an electrically driven thermostat, maintained at $26^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$. Appropriate correction for residual current were made for all currents reported and in calculating the diffusion current. Maxima suppressor was found to be unnecessary in these determinations.

Effect of Variation of Height.—A series of polarograms of 1.0 m mole Mo (VI) in aqueous sulphuric acid (0.1M) using sodium sulphate (0.2M) as base electrolyte were drawn at five different heights of mercury column (25–50 cms). The values of $id/h^{\frac{1}{2}}$ effect are given in the Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of Change of Mercury Pressure on Wave Height

Height of capillary dipped in solution — 1 cm.
Back pressure—1.135 cms of Mercury.

Height in cms.	Mass of Hg in mg/sec.	Drop time in secs.	int	h _{eff.} (in cms)	i_d after correction	$i_d/h^{\frac{1}{2}}$ effect
22.2	3.9	5.14	20.309	20.065	2.1375	0.4489
26.9	4.6	4.40	20.310	24.765	2.2275	0.4461
31.3	5.5	3.70	20.307	29.165	2.4525	0.4539
33.9	6.3	3.24	20.306	32.065	2.6550	0.4401
37.9	7.02	2.92	20.308	36.765	2.7675	0.4398

Constant value of $id/h^{\frac{1}{2}}$ effect reveals that the wave is diffusion controlled.

Effect of Temperature:—The polarogram of Na_2MoO_4 (1.0)m mole in presence of 0.1M H_2SO_4 and 0.2M sodium sulphate were drawn at five different temperatures (25–54°). The values of temperatures were calculated using the method employed by Nejedly⁶ and are presented in the table given below.

TABLE II

Effect of Variation of Temperature

Temperature °C	i_d in Ma	Ratio of i_d at indicated temperature and i_d at 26°C.	Temperature coefficient.
26	2.0175	1.000	—
36.5	2.430	1.208	3.8%
42	2.677	1.358	2.5%
49	3.057	1.506	2.1%
53	3.645	1.811	3.9%

The higher (more than 1.3% per degree) and variable values of temperature coefficient of diffusion current suggest that the wave produced by Mo (VI) in 0.1*M* sulphuric acid using sodium sulphate as base electrolyte is catalytic.

Effect of Concentration:—Polarograms of solutions containing different concentrations of sodium molybdate in 0.1*M* sulphuric acid using 0.2*M* sodium sulphate as base electrolyte were drawn. The values of i_d/c are given in the table given below.

TABLE III
Effect of Concentration on Wave Height

No.	Concn.	i_d in μA	i_d/c	$K = i_d/Cm^{2/3} t^{1/6}$
1.	0.3mM	0.675	2.250	534.0
2.	0.5mM	1.170	2.300	529.0
3.	0.9mM	1.710	2.235	538.1
4.	1.0mM	2.235	2.202	534.1
5.	1.5mM	3.303	2.225	534.5

The results show that values of i_d/c and K are constant. The wave A tends to merge in wave B at the concentration of about 0.5mM but in dilute solutions the wave A is more pronounced as is clear from the data in table No. IV.

TABLE IV
The Values of Diffusion Current in Dilute Solutions

Concn. in millimole	-0.15V	i_d at	-0.90V
0.05	0.08360		0.02464
0.07	0.01180		0.003542
0.11	0.01892		0.0572
0.16	0.02728		0.07008

The diffusion current for the first reduction stage is approximately one third as large as the diffusion current for the over-all reduction. This suggests that Mo(VI) is reduced to Mo(V) at the potential of first step and that Mo(III) is the product of complete reduction. The alternative possibility of reduction to Mo(IV) and then to metallic molybdenum is unlikely because it conflicts with the known electrochemical characteristics of molybdate solutions.

From the waves it is clear that the reduction of Mo(V) occurs in two unequal steps whose combined wave heights indicate reduction to Mo(III). The relative magnitudes of waves B and C has been found to vary with the molybdate concentration of the solution. It is clear from the figure that wave B is proportionally greater and wave C is correspondingly smaller in more dilute solutions. From the results it is obvious that direct reduction to Mo(III) occurs rather than successive reduction to Mo(IV) and then to Mo(III). In order to explain the mechanism of the reduction of Mo(VI) it may be suggested that the occurrence of two molybdenum(V) to Mo(III) reduction steps. (1) The Mo(V) formed by initial reduction of Mo(VI) exists in two forms reducible at different potential. (2) The reduction product Mo(III) for each wave is different.

Heyrovsky and Ilkovic⁷ equation shows that each reduction wave is irreversible. The half wave potentials of three reduction waves A, B and C in 0.1M H₂SO₄ and 0.2M Na₂SO₄ are +0.06, -0.29 and -0.60 volts respectively.

FIG. 1

Effect of pH.—Polarograms containing 1 mmole sodium molybdate, 0.2M Na₂SO₄ and different amounts of sulphuric acid were drawn and it was found that well defined waves were obtained in 0.1M H₂SO₄ and 0.2M Na₂SO₄. At lower pH the height of wave C goes on decreasing and in excess of acid the wave C is completely vanished as shown in figures. The results are in agreement with the results of Johnson and Robinson⁸.

FIG. 2

Determination of Molybdenum in presence of Vanadium.—Vanadium gives an anodic wave in aqueous H₂SO₄ acid using Na₂SO₄ as a supporting electrolyte whereas Mo (VI) undergoes reduction giving three waves under similar conditions. First wave is due to the reduction of Mo (VI) to Mo (V) and the other two waves are probably due to the reduction

7. Heyrovsky, J. and Ilkovic, D., *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1935, 7, 198.

of Mo (IV) to Mo (III). Half wave potential of first wave of Mo (VI) is at $+0.06$ volts which does interfere with that of vanadium. Hence the determination of Mo (VI) has been done

FIG. 3

with the help of waves B & C. From Mo (V) to Mo (III) as the corresponding amount of Mo (V) is obtained from Mo (VI). Thus the estimation of Mo (VI) may be carried out in presence of vanadium. Method of standard addition has been used.

TABLE V

Mix. No.	Vanadium present in gms.	Molybdenum present in gms.	Molybdenum found in gms.	Error.
1.	0.71015	0.24205	0.24005	0.8%
2.	0.14203	0.29046	0.28803	0.9%
3.	2.13045	0.38728	0.37810	0.2%
4.	0.01775	0.43569	0.43134	0.9%
5.	0.021304	0.14523	0.144280	—
6.	0.56812	0.19464	0.193460	0.5%

Determination of Mo (VI) in presence of W (VI).—Tungsten is not reduced at D.M.E. in aqueous sulphuric acid using sodium sulphate as supporting electrolyte but when present in large excess along with Mo (VI), it does interfere in the determination of Mo (VI) as it increases the height of the wave. But when concn. of Mo (VI) is hundred times greater as compared to the concn. of tungsten, it has been found possible to estimate Mo (VI) in presence of tungsten to an accuracy of 2%. Presence of tungsten causes the wave due to hydrogen to start at more +Ve potentials.

FIG. 4

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